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The IPBES Data and Knowledge Management Policy

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Editors:

Rainer M. Krug and Aidin Niamir

Contributors to this revision in alphabetical order:

Douglas Beard, Maral Dadvar, Brenda Daly, Adriana De Palma, Debora Pignatari Drucker, Golda Edwin, Renske Gudde, Kwame Oppong Hackman, Jessica Hetzer, Rainer M. Krug, Milan Mataruga, Aidin Niamir, Benedict A. Omare, Ricardo Pinto-Coelho, Hanno Seebens, Yanina Sica, Aysegul Sirakaya, Zheping Xu, and Mayra Alejandra Zurbaran Nucci.

Contributors to previous revisions in alphabetical order:

Wouter Addink, Gregoire Dubois, Renske Gudde, Joy Kumagai, Rainer M. Krug, Cornelia Krug, Howard Nelson, Aidin Niamir, Benedict A. Omare, Fatima Parker-Allie, Debora Pignatari Drucker, and David Thau.

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Inquiries should be directed to mea-ipbes-secretariat@un.org

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Introduction

This policy builds on the data and information management plan approved by the IPBES Plenary set out in annex II to decision IPBES-3/1, and the earlier revision of the IPBES data and knowledge management policy welcomed by the IPBES Plenary at its ninth session, set out in IPBES/9/INF/14, appendix II to the annex, and the most recent version outlined in IPBES/11/INF/26. It builds specifically on the activity “reviewing and developing data and metadata guidelines”, and is grounded in its principles for “managing knowledge, information, and data” in the Platform, in particular open science and accessibility. Definitions of the terms used throughout this document can be found in annex A.

- **Open science.** The open science approach promotes the generation of knowledge through collaboration based on free and open access to knowledge, information, and data. Open science, therefore, ensures that the work of all the IPBES experts and stakeholders involved in the development of an IPBES product is fully recognised, properly attributed, documented, and preserved. Adoption of the open science approach and principles means a significant cultural change in the way science-policy is conducted, and the outcome of knowledge synthesis and the underlying workflows are shared publicly. In the context of the Platform, the open science approach brings very significant advances in transparency, data integration, analysis and interpretation and could ultimately lead to a better understanding of nature and its contribution to human well-being.
- **Accessibility.** A core value of the Platform is free and open access to its deliverables and to the material on which they are based. Consequently, the policy will aim for open, sustained access to data and information sources for its deliverables (e.g., in the scientific literature) with as few restrictions as possible; enforce the use of common and accessible, non-proprietary file formats in the Platform’s deliverables; emphasise the need to make data and knowledge available; and facilitate multilingual discovery and sharing of data and knowledge wherever possible. The Platform acknowledges that making data and information accessible may not always mean it is openly and freely accessible to all IPBES members and stakeholders; this includes considerations with regard to Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) and Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLCs), as technical, economic, political or other reasons may limit accessibility, but not its findability.
- **Inclusivity and collective benefit.** Cooperation in knowledge synthesis and broad acceptance of the resulting IPBES products is essential for the Platform to fulfil its mandate. For the acceptance and cooperation of stakeholders and data and knowledge holders, inclusivity in all stages of the knowledge synthesis is essential, and IPBES takes many steps to try to enhance participation with all stakeholders, including IPLCs. IPBES acknowledges the richness of diverse knowledge systems, including ILK, and the diversity of knowledge holders and producers, including IPLCs.
- **Responsible and ethical use of advances in data technologies.** The ethical and responsible use of advances in data technologies, in particular generative artificial intelligence (AI), ensures the appropriate use of these technologies and fosters trust in the Platform. The use of AI should be grounded in transparency, accountability, and acknowledgement of potential biases. The values of inclusivity, accessibility, and collective benefit should be considered in the use of AI. This approach supports the equitable advancement of knowledge and ensures that the use of AI benefits IPBES products in accordance with this policy and the Code of Practice on the ethical and responsible use of AI.

Thus, this policy follows, regarding data and knowledge management within IPBES, the overarching strategies of UNEP, policies and guidelines, to the maximum extent possible within the mandate of the Platform, allowing IPBES members and stakeholders, including IPLCs and other interested parties, to use and access IPBES products, and data collected or documented during their production and consequently derive benefit from them. IPBES has recognised the importance of ILK for the conservation and sustainable use of ecosystems, and detailed procedures and protocols to be used with regard to ILK and the engagement with IPLCs have been developed. From its inception, the Platform

aims to enhance interrelationships and complementarities between different knowledge systems. By promoting transparency, inclusivity, and the ethical use of data and technologies, this policy contributes to building and maintaining trust among all knowledge holders and users.

Objectives

To fulfil its function to produce scientifically robust and transparent assessments, IPBES is committed to implementing data and knowledge management procedures that are discipline-appropriate, practical, cost-effective, sustainable, and supportive of its objectives. This data and knowledge management policy is the primary reference document for IPBES data and knowledge management. It serves to ensure that data and knowledge are managed correctly and consistently, are maintained to the highest possible standard, and contribute to building trust through transparent processes.

The data and knowledge management policy has the following objectives:

- a. To ensure that data and knowledge produced during IPBES knowledge synthesis activities follow legal obligations and the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and CARE principles for Indigenous data governance (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics) to the fullest extent possible within the mandate of the Platform;
- b. To ensure that IPBES products, to the maximum extent possible within the mandate of the Platform, are openly available and designed so they are accessible, allowing all scientists, IPBES members, IPLCs and other stakeholders to use them and consequently derive and share the benefits from them, thereby fostering transparency and trust;
- c. To give full consideration the use of advances in data technology, in particular AI, based on existing and evolving principles and guidelines for the applicability and ethical and responsible use;
- d. To provide guidance to all IPBES entities, including the secretariat and IPBES experts, to fulfil their responsibilities with respect to the management, handling, preservation and distribution of data and knowledge, generated data, and IPBES products within the Platform;
- e. To provide guidance for the long-term storage and preservation of IPBES products to the IPBES experts;
- f. To promote the usage of open-source software to enable users to recreate and use IPBES products without limitations;
- g. To guide the IPBES experts to fulfil their responsibilities to develop the necessary data and knowledge management reports (DMRs), which fulfil the requirements of this policy and support consistency, transparency and accountability in data practices.

General principles

IPBES products and the associated knowledge synthesis should be managed following the FAIR and CARE principles to the fullest extent possible within the mandate of the Platform throughout their life cycle, in line with the commitment to open science and accessibility, as these are essential for fulfilling the functions of IPBES: to perform regular and timely assessments of knowledge on nature, its contributions to a good quality of life and their interlinkages, in a transparent and reproducible manner. IPBES products and associated knowledge synthesis relating to IPLCs or their knowledge should follow the IPBES approach to recognising and working with ILK (annex II to decision IPBES-5/1).

In the management, handling and delivery of IPBES products, international, regional and national law should be complied with, which includes access and benefit-sharing, sovereign rights over genetic resources, rights of privacy, intellectual property rights, data governance regulations and confidentiality duties. If necessary, IPBES products should be anonymised before long-term storage and publication.

IPBES experts are encouraged to take advantage of advances in data technologies and to make best use of these digital tools throughout the assessment process and in the preparation of IPBES products. These technologies should be used responsibly, with particular attention to ethics, transparency and underlying biases. The use of AI within IPBES should be precautionary, following the Principles for the Ethical Use of Artificial Intelligence in the United Nations System and the UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence. IPBES provides guidance to all IPBES experts to ensure that they are aware of and follow IPBES procedures.

Application

This data and knowledge management policy will be applied to all new and on-going IPBES products and related knowledge synthesis. The policy should be reviewed at least every two years by the task force on data and knowledge management to adapt to new developments in these principles, taking full account of existing and evolving principles and guidelines on the applicability and ethical use of advances in data technology. Exceptions and deviations from this policy will be reviewed by the technical support unit on data and knowledge management and the secretariat, and submitted for approval to the Management Committee, and documented in a corresponding data management report (DMR).

Scope

This policy applies to all IPBES products and knowledge synthesis. IPBES experts are required to abide by the terms and conditions agreed with third parties. The current IPBES data and knowledge management policy also recognises that the policies of third parties are evolving and that they may require higher levels of data accessibility and dissemination in the future.

Compliance and enforcement

Compliance with the data and knowledge management policy is mandatory for all IPBES entities involved in the preparation of IPBES products. Compliance will be monitored by the technical support unit on data and knowledge management. Products will not be accepted as IPBES products unless they comply with this policy. The roles and responsibilities for the implementation of this policy and the production of IPBES products compliant with all IPBES data-related tasks are distributed among all IPBES entities according to their roles. The detailed roles and responsibilities are outlined in annex B.

Provisions on data and knowledge management reporting

- a. DMR is expected for each IPBES task. This can be achieved by a single DMR covering all the analyses and work for an entire IPBES task, or by separate DMRs for each subtask, such as an analysis or the development of one figure, within an IPBES task.
- b. DMR can consist of the report and, optionally, multiple additional documents. When it contains multiple documents, the actual DMR — the main document — can be considered an overview document that provides transparency on the methods, with the additional documents providing more technical background for reproducibility.
- c. All activities and outputs related to data and knowledge management must comply with this policy. If full compliance is not possible within assessment related tasks, the responsible experts and the relevant assessment technical support unit must clearly specify and justify any exceptions in the DMR. Such exceptions will be reviewed by the technical support unit on data and

- knowledge management and the secretariat, and submitted for approval to the Management Committee.
- d. IPBES experts are responsible for ensuring that DMRs are created, maintained and updated throughout the life cycle of each task and submitted to the relevant assessment technical support unit in time for the next milestone. The technical support units, both for assessments and for data and knowledge management, will provide guidance, templates and support to assist experts in the preparation and maintenance of DMRs, ensuring consistency with this policy.
 - e. The technical support unit on data and knowledge management provides support and, where appropriate, guidelines and examples to the IPBES experts to make sure that FAIR and CARE principles are followed to the fullest extent possible within the mandate of the Platform for data and knowledge management and documentation in the DMRs.
 - f. The task force and the technical support unit on ILK provide support and, where appropriate, guidelines and examples to the IPBES experts to make sure that the FAIR and CARE principles are followed to the fullest extent possible within the mandate of the Platform for data and knowledge management and documentation in the DMRs, where such data relate to ILK or IPLCs.
 - g. The secretariat provides information about recommended long-term, and to the extent possible certified, open data repositories that provide digital object identifiers (DOIs).

Provisions on accessibility, inclusivity and collective benefit

- a. IPBES products should be preserved, including a DOI for each milestone of a task.
- b. IPBES products, including those in or associated with an assessment such as DMRs, should be made openly accessible in a form that follows this policy at the latest six months after the approval or acceptance of the assessment, or approval or acknowledgement of other IPBES products by the Plenary. Data and knowledge related to milestones should also be made accessible, as far as confidentiality rules allow. Embargo periods are possible but need to be communicated with the secretariat in advance. Restricted access to the IPBES data underlying IPBES products is mandatory until approval of the assessment by the Plenary, with the exception of the external review periods. After approval, restricted access is only allowed under special circumstances and needs to be assessed by the secretariat and approved by the Management Committee and communicated to the secretariat.
- c. Applicable ethical, privacy, confidentiality and data governance requirements need to be followed and generated data, if deemed necessary, must be anonymised before preservation.
- d. Tools for the finding, processing and final presentation of any data should be used in a responsible and ethical manner that follows this policy. No tools should be used without critical assessment of the methods and results by the experts.
- e. The management, handling and delivery of materials from IPLCs adhere to the FAIR and CARE principles to the fullest extent possible as outlined in this policy, as well as to other binding conditions outside this policy in accordance with international, regional and national law.
- f. IPBES products and their metadata should be released with a clear and accessible licence. Allowed licences for IPBES products are Creative Commons By Attribution (CC-BY) or licences equivalent to these, which permit users to copy, distribute and transmit work, and adapt work under the condition that the user must attribute the work in the manner specified by IPBES. Divergent licences need to be approved by the technical support unit on data and knowledge management.
- g. All knowledge synthesis within IPBES has to be conducted in accordance with agreements with the holders of the data and knowledge regarding use, reuse, presentation and procedures. Communication with IPLCs needs to be maintained over the whole task cycle to the extent

possible within the mandate of the Platform to provide feedback to the knowledge holders and include feedback from the knowledge holders in the knowledge synthesis, as outlined in the IPBES approach to recognising and working with ILK (annex II to decision IPBES-5/1).

- h. IPBES products will be made available and accessible to the holders of the data and knowledge, in line with agreed terms documented during ILK dialogue workshops or other activities, with due consideration to the FAIR and CARE principles.

Provisions on the use of advances in data technologies

- a. IPBES experts are encouraged to make use of advances in data technology, provided their use is compliant with this policy and applicable IPBES codes of practice, and follows a precautionary approach.
- b. AI systems may introduce risks, particularly in the interpretation and application of results, which require careful consideration to prevent negative consequences.
- c. The use of AI in IPBES tasks, where permitted, must remain transparent, with well-documented prompts.
- d. Further guidance and examples of ethical and responsible AI use are provided in the IPBES code of practice on the use of artificial intelligence, tailored to the needs of assessments. This includes alignment with the FAIR and CARE principles to ensure that AI systems contribute to just, transparent and inclusive knowledge synthesis.

Annex A: Glossary

- Access and benefit-sharing.** Rooted in the CARE principles, this refers to the understanding that data, knowledge or resources should be used in ways that benefit the community or group from which they originate. This principle ensures that the interests of the community are prioritised and that any use of data or resources contributes positively to their well-being and development.
- Accessible.** Refers to the ease with which data, knowledge and IPBES products can be found, retrieved and used by all intended audiences, including IPBES members, IPLCs and other stakeholders. Accessibility implies that information is available in formats and languages that are understandable and usable, with minimal technical, legal or financial barriers, and that support discoverability and inclusiveness.
- AI (artificial intelligence).** AI models are trained with large amounts of data. These models and prompts can be embedded in interfaces that resemble familiar tools (for example, literature search engines or grammar checkers). In this document, AI refers to all tools that directly interact with generative AI (for example, chatbots) or use AI in the background. The term is limited to generative AI systems.
- CARE.** A set of guiding principles for Indigenous data governance, focusing on the appropriate use and reuse of Indigenous data and knowledge. CARE stands for Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics. These principles should also be applied to the management of knowledge.
- Citations and references.** A citation refers to the source of information supporting IPBES deliverables, addressing where the information came from. A reference includes sufficient details to make the source findable and traceable.
- Collective benefit.** Benefits for all. In the context of this policy, these are direct benefits resulting from the use of and access to IPBES products, and knowledge and data gathered or documented during their production and from sharing credit. To this end, IPBES products and associated knowledge and data should, to the maximum extent possible, be openly available and designed so they are accessible to all, allowing scientists, IPLCs and others to use them and derive benefit from them.
- Data.** Data can be of any nature: spatial or non-spatial, qualitative or quantitative, descriptive, and from all scientific disciplines. This includes information from IPLCs.
- Data and knowledge.** Data and knowledge often form a continuum, where data cannot be interpreted without knowledge. They include individual units of information obtained from observations, measurements, experiences or value systems, and form the basis for monitoring, synthesis, assessments and analysis.
- Data deposit package.** The content deposited in a long-term repository. Each package has a DOI and consists of the data and knowledge and a DMR describing them.
- DMR (data and knowledge management report).** A document that forms part of each IPBES assessment and associated tasks, detailing how data and knowledge are handled throughout the process. It includes information on data creation, references, scripts, software used and access provisions, and must be updated throughout the duration of the task or assessment.
- DOI (digital object identifier).** A digital identifier for a physical or digital object, defined in the DOI Handbook and recognised under ISO 26324:2012. Provides a persistent and interoperable link.
- Ethical and responsible use.** The ethical and responsible use of AI involves ensuring that its development and application uphold human rights, dignity and fairness, and that AI systems contribute to sustainable development and the well-being of people and the planet. It requires transparency, accountability, inclusiveness, reliability, safety and respect for privacy.
- External data and knowledge.** Data and knowledge generated outside IPBES and published in peer-reviewed journals, grey literature or available as ILK. While IPBES is not responsible for

preserving these, it must preserve metadata describing the data's provenance, licensing and copyright information when such knowledge is used, with agreement from knowledge holders.

FAIR. A set of guiding principles for making data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. These should also be applied to knowledge management.

Generative AI. AI that produces content such as images, code or text in response to user input. Well-known examples include chatbots.

ILK (Indigenous and local knowledge). As defined in the IPBES assessment glossaries, Indigenous and local knowledge systems are "social and ecological knowledge, practices and beliefs concerning relationships among living beings and their environments." See also annex II to decision IPBES-5/1, which describes them as "dynamic bodies of integrated, holistic, social and ecological knowledge, practices and beliefs pertaining to the relationship of living beings, including people, with one another and with their environments."

Knowledge. Understanding developed through experience, reasoning and learning. Essential for interpreting associated data.

Knowledge synthesis. All IPBES activities that collect, measure, integrate or analyse data or knowledge, including ILK. Also includes documentation of ILK from dialogue workshops or IPLC activities.

Milestone. A significant step in an IPBES task or assessment that warrants long-term storage. For assessments, this includes all drafts prepared for internal and external reviews as well as final versions of chapters.

Workflow. A repeatable set of steps for achieving a goal, such as data gathering, analysis and visualisation. Workflows document the scientific process, including tools and software used.

Annex B: Roles and responsibilities

Bureau and MEP

- review any changes to the policy as proposed by the task force on data and knowledge, and consider these for approval.

Secretariat

- execute, under the guidance of the task force on data and knowledge and in cooperation with the technical support unit (TSU) on data and knowledge management, the development and maintenance of guidelines, tutorials, workflows and examples to enable IPBES experts to implement this policy.
- maintain an accurate, up-to-date and accessible list of citations and references (including rich metadata), as well as links to external data and knowledge, and knowledge and generated data used in IPBES products.

Task force on data and knowledge management

- develop and provide guidelines and examples for data and knowledge management, and guide their development and maintenance.
- advise the TSU on data and knowledge management.
- review the policy at least every two years.
- determine procedures that comply with legal requirements and fulfil the FAIR and CARE principles, including through collaboration with the ILK task force, to the fullest extent possible within the Platform's mandate.
- review the annexes, guidelines, tutorials, workflows and examples related to this policy annually to identify gaps and implement new developments.

Task force on ILK

- work with the task force on data and knowledge to review the policy, at least every two years, with regard to aspects relating to IPLCs and ILK, including determining procedures that fulfil FAIR and CARE principles to the fullest extent possible within the Platform's mandate.
- review the guidelines, tutorials, workflows and examples related to this policy, particularly with regard to aspects relating to IPLCs and ILK, on a yearly basis to identify gaps and implement new developments.

TSU on data and knowledge management

- provide support, advice and participate in efforts from the task force on data and knowledge management, and execute, under guidance and in cooperation with the secretariat, the development and maintenance of guidelines, tutorials, workflows and examples to enable IPBES to implement this policy.
- review the DMRs from corresponding assessment TSUs to ensure alignment with the data and knowledge management policy.
- ensure that assessment TSUs follow the data and knowledge management policy, fulfil their responsibilities as outlined in this policy and in the DMRs, and will collect metadata of the IPBES products from the TSUs to ensure accessibility and discoverability.
- provide guidance to IPBES experts on the responsible use of advances in data technologies.

TSU on Indigenous and local knowledge

- provide support, advice and participate in efforts from the task force on data and knowledge management to develop guidelines and examples for data and knowledge management and reporting when working with ILK and in alignment with CARE principles.
- support the implementation of these guidelines in IPBES assessments and other processes.
- review DMRs upon request from the TSU on data and knowledge management to ensure alignment with ILK and IPLC considerations.

Assessment TSU

- collect the DMRs from IPBES experts involved in assessments.
- assist experts in ensuring DMRs adhere to this policy.
- assign a persistent identifier (for example, DOI) for each data deposit package.
- add consistent, specific, and descriptive keywords and metadata (for example, chapter, assessment, figure) to make data findable and identifiable.
- ensure that IPBES experts fulfil responsibilities as outlined in this policy and the DMRs, and will collect product metadata for transfer to the task force on data and knowledge management.
- develop and maintain, under the guidance of the TSU on data and knowledge management and in cooperation with the secretariat, guidelines, tutorials, workflows and examples (DMRs) to enable implementation of this policy.
- check for retracted references in IPBES products, ensuring these are replaced prior to the final milestone.
- collect and provide feedback to the TSU on data and knowledge management on lessons learned during policy implementation.

IPBES experts

- prepare and keep DMRs up to date for all IPBES-related knowledge synthesis activities. DMRs should be available by the first milestone and updated for each subsequent milestone, conforming to this policy and the technical guidelines.
- responsible for implementing the DMRs and reporting to the relevant assessment TSU.
- responsible for the ethical, transparent and validated use of AI, particularly in line with responsible use principles.